

resistant varieties as possible replacements for locally grown Mangala

(see table). The most promising varieties were IET7633 and IET7614, both of

Rasi Finegora, and IET7261 from Rasi Mettasamma. *ℳ*

BG367-4, a promising short-duration rice

K. Ganesan, T. Sundaram, W. W. Manuel, and S. Palanisamy, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Ambasamudram 627401, Tamil Nadu, India

BG3674 (BG280-12/PTB 33) is a promising short-duration rice received through the International Rice Testing

Program. It was evaluated at PES in the 1980 International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON), and performed well in 1980-84 in Jun-Sep.

BG367-4 yielded 9.5 t ha in 1983, with average yields of 6.5 t ha over 4 yr. It yielded 25% more than TKM9 and 35% more than ADT36 (see table). Duration ranged from 109 to 115 d, averaging 112 d.

BG3674 has semidwarf (91 cm)

stature, long slender grains, and white rice. The 1,000-grain weight is 23.4 g.

Yield potential is high because of high panicle weight (1.33 g).

The variety has been nominated for the 1985-86 Rice Coordinated Yield Trial-2 (100-120 d) at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University experiment stations and is being used as a donor in the PES hybridization program. *ℳ*

Performance of BG367-4 at Ambasamudram, India, 1980-84.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)						Flowering time (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill	1000-grain wt (g)	Panicle wt (g)
	IRON 1980	Yield trial 1981	Yield trial 1982	IRYN (VE) 1983	Yield trial 1984	IRYN (VE) 1984					
BG3674	6.9	5.5	5.1	9.5	6.1	6.1	82	91	8.3	23.4	1.33
ADT36	5.1	4.4	5.2	—	4.1	5.4	84	84	8.9	24.2	1.16
TKM9	—	5.0	5.3	6.6	4.3	4.6	82	82	8.2	24.5	1.27
m + σ	6.9	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
CD (P = 0.05)	—	1.1	0.5	1.4	0.1	1.3	—	—	—	—	—

Evaluation of six rice genotypes in relation to field hydrology

I.K. Jaggi, R.O. Das, and D.C. Bisen, Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Zonal Agricultural Research Station, Labhandi, Raipur, Madhya Pradesh, India

We evaluated the effect of drought on yield of six rices with different durations in 1983 wet and 1984 semiwet seasons.

In both seasons, the rices were planted on 7 Sep and grown with similar agronomic practices. Weekly precipitation, evaporation, daily groundwater level, and flowering time were recorded (Fig. 1). Drought was longer and more severe in semiwet season. Evaporation exceeded precipitation 11 wk after seeding in semiwet season and after 16 wk in wet season. In semiwet season, groundwater level was below 80 cm 12 wk after seeding.

Short-duration MW 10 performed best in semiwet season, yielding 2.5 t/ha. Late-maturing Mahsuri yielded lowest, 0.3 t/ha. Poorva, IR36, Usha, and Safri 17 produced intermediate yields. Safri 17

Water table depth (cm)

Weekly evaporation and rainfall (mm)

1. Weekly precipitation, evaporation, daily groundwater level, and flowering time of 6 genotypes. Kaipur, India

2. Effect of subsurface water level on rainfed rice, Raipur, India.

was less susceptible to drought than Mahsuri. It had less leaf rolling and high root density.

Figure 2 shows the role of subsurface water in rainfed culture. The groundwater level fell during the

cropping season. Longer duration rices suffered more drought stress and yields declined. Subsoil moisture (30-80 cm deep) was particularly important to medium and late duration varieties in semiwet season (see table). *ℒ*

Effect of subsoil moisture on 6 rice genotypes, Raipur, India.

	Poorva	MW10	IR36	Usha	Safri 17	Mahsuri
<i>Grain yield^a (t/ha)</i>						
Wet	2.5	3.5	2.8	3.0	2.7	3.1
Semiwet	2.0	3.5	1.8	1.3	1.0	0.3
Mean	2.3	3.5	2.3	2.2	1.9	1.7
<i>Reduction (%) in yield</i>						
	18	0	35	57	62	91
<i>Subsoil moisture contribution (%)</i>						
	21	32	41	57	61	
^a CD at 5%	Season 0.4		Genotypes 0.3		Interaction 0.4	

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DISEASE RESISTANCE

Scented rices with stem rot (SR) and bacterial blight (BB) resistance

K. Singh, H. Chand, and D. Singh, Haryana Agricultural University Rice Research Station (HAURRS), Kaul, Haryana, India

SR, caused by *Sclerotium oryzae*, and BB, caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, reduce rice yields in Haryana. We evaluated 68 scented rices for their reaction to these diseases at HAURRS in 1983-84 and 1984-85.

To screen for BB resistance, each entry was planted in 2-m rows at 20 × 15-cm spacing. Plants were clip-inoculated with a BB suspension 21 d after transplanting (DT) for kresek and 45 DT for leaf blight and rated for resistance using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

SR screening was in field and laboratory. In the laboratory, cut stem

pieces were wound-inoculated with a small piece of agar-cultured *S. oryzae*. Inoculated stems were kept standing in a test tube rack in a tray with 2.5 cm of water. They were covered with plastic bags to maintain high humidity and were incubated at 28-30°C. Lesion length was measured 10 d after inoculation. Entries with lesions less than 10 mm long were considered resistant; those with 10-30 mm lesions, moderately resistant; and those with lesions more than 30 mm long, susceptible.

HKR220 was resistant to SR in laboratory tests in both seasons. HKR216 and HKR219 were resistant in the field. Pak basmati and RPSC 136 were SK resistant in all tests. They are a good source of SR resistance for breeding purposes.

Pak basmati also was moderately resistant at the kresek phase of BB.

RP2144-108-5-3-2 and NDR 601 also had moderate resistance to kresek. However, none of the materials were resistant to both BB phases. *ℒ*

Rice seedling resistance to brown spot (BS)

K. K. Baloch and J. M. Bonman, Plant Pathology Department IIRI

We tested 15 rice varieties for seedling resistance to isolates of *Bipolaris oryzae* the BS fungus. In the greenhouse, 23-d-old seedlings were artificially inoculated with 3 isolates using a spore concentration of 3×10^4 spores/ml. Disease was measured on the 3d fully expanded leaf as lesion number per cm² and lesion size (mm²), and percent diseased leaf area was calculated.